

MODEL OF FORMATION OF PRACTICAL KNOWLEDGE BASED ON TEACHING TECHNICAL MECHANICS IN STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Maqolada oliy o'quv yurtlarida bo'lajak muhandislik bakalavrlarini texnik mexanikaga asoslangan kasbga tayyorlash yo'nalishlari ko'rib chiqiladi. Bitirgandan so'ng, muallif mashinasozlik bakalavrlarini kasbiy tayyorlash muammolarini tahlil qildi.

Introduction. Modeling is important at this stage in the development of education. As a result of radical changes in educational paradigms, there are new requirements for modeling innovative pedagogical systems. The importance of "modeling" in the practice of pedagogical science describes the meaningful aspect of educational activity and reflects the innovations that have emerged in the goals, means, methods and forms of activity. In this case, modeling serves as a special and unique type of pedagogical activity that is closely related to research, diagnosis, design, planning, programming, social management. Modeling of pedagogical systems involves the targeted creation of new pedagogical, didactic, methodological and technological education systems, primarily in the form of advanced ideas, ie in the form of a model and then through its implementation. In this case, it is necessary not only to study the existing experience, but also to create

something that does not yet exist on the basis of theoretical research.

Model:

- certain type of project;
- some "ideal" model in which other objects of this type can be copied;
- is understood as material processing of the object, regardless of the purpose for which it is carried out.

The model of the education system performs the following functions:

- practical (when using the essential features of the object of reproduction);
- cognitive (when the object performs educational functions (for example, models, diagrams, tables, pictures), to ensure the success of the acquisition of ready knowledge;
- research (the object is modeled in order to obtain new values).

Models are used to solve the following pedagogical tasks:

- development of pedagogical theories and concepts, if its direct study is limited due to the current level of knowledge and practice;
- explain the evidence and the law;
- forecasting the condition of the object in the future;
- determine the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the classification of the object;
- check for technical or other proposed conditions;
- to compile scientific theories [S.M.Markova]

Development of a model of the process of formation of practical knowledge among students of technical specialties in the teaching of mechanics, in particular, the work of V.I.Andreev, I.Y.Lerner, M.I.Mahmutov, M.N.Skatkin, A.V.Khutorskoy. identifying the mechanisms that provide, finding different connections, and bringing them into a single holistic picture.

The leading foundations of the following model are presented with several blocks.

The model scheme (its form) is taken from the dissertation research by N.I.Mokritskaya, developed and adapted by the author. An active approach to the process of formation and development of practical knowledge in the teaching of mechanics in higher education institutions is aimed at the formation of practical skills in the future active, professional techniques, self-understanding as a subject in new technical and economic conditions.

Method. From the point of view of the activity approach, the model considered in this research is the internal structure of the structures created by this set of goals, the integrated content, forms, methods, holistic form characterized by the socialization of the individual, higher education in teaching

mechanics aimed at the formation and development of practical knowledge in students of educational institutions. The components of the model of the process of formation of practical knowledge in students of higher education institutions in the teaching of mechanics are: purpose, principles, functions, content, forms, methods, teaching aids and outcomes.

The purpose of strengthening the basic model of the process of formation of practical knowledge in higher education institutions in the teaching of mechanics is as follows:

- formation of practical knowledge;
- formation of technical thinking;
- preparation for future careers.

The target component assumes the development of functions for the formation of practical knowledge in the educational activities of students (teaching, development, upbringing, professional). The following didactic principles were used in this study to develop the content of the formation of practical skills in teaching technical mechanics to students of construction specialties:

- research involving the study of categories based on basic laws, concepts, and educational activities;
- systematization achieved through the development and implementation of a comprehensive approach that covers all types of classroom and extracurricular activities;
- where each new knowledge is based on the previous one;
- sequence is the planning of the content for the formation of practical knowledge and skills among students, and each new knowledge is developed in an ascending direction, based on the previous one and arising from it;

- encourages learning through the use of discussions, possible solutions to psychological and pedagogical situations, research tasks, problems;
- the theory of the relationship between theory and practice, combining theoretical knowledge with practical research activities in the laboratory - extracurricular, extracurricular and independent;
- the suitability of students for their age (2nd year) depends on their individual characteristics.

The component content of the model includes two additional elements: a set of actual normative knowledge in accordance with the requirements of the State Education Standard for Higher Education Institutions; to change socially important standards as a source of future technology in the form of self-development.

Systematization of knowledge and skills acquired in the study of technical mechanics (practical mechanics, technical mechanics) is aimed at mastering the stages of composition and tasks at an understandable level; the practical knowledge and skills acquired should be put into practice.

The model also includes an organizational and management component that involves dialectical correspondence between teacher and student self-management functions, the objectives and essence of the presentation of the learning material, i.e., the main components. : type of management, type of information process, characterized by the types of means of transmitting information management of cognitive activity. The organizational and management component requires the introduction of rational forms, methods, and tools to study and manage the process of forming practical knowledge in the study of mechanics.

The optimal combination of methods plays an important role in the educational process. Thus, different methods of teaching connect all types of emotional perception to the acquisition of knowledge - sight and hearing, which makes perception more effective, the active perception of learning material by students with different types of memory and mental activity ensures the activation of students' cognitive activity, allows to best take into account the specific features of different sections of the educational material, helps to develop students' abilities in the best possible way. Introducing the definitions of the teaching method, I.Y.Lerner states that the teaching method is a system of teacher's actions, which organizes the practical and cognitive activities of the student, which leads to a stable mastery of the content of teaching.

Y.K.Babansky focused on the problem of choosing the optimal combination of teaching methods in the optimization of the educational process. He emphasizes the need to take a number of intermediate steps in choosing teaching methods:

- decide on a rational combination of verbal, visual and practical methods; about the combination of teacher management methods and independent student work; about the combination of methods of stimulating and motivating learning; methods of control and self-government;
- identify the dominant combination of methods for this phase of training;
- think of backup options for combining methods.

Optimal conduct of the educational process involves the integrated use of methods and teaching aids through their rational integration. In the process of education on the formation and development of practical knowledge among students of construction

specialties in the teaching of mechanics, this research work includes: oral (explanation, lecture, conversation, discussion, etc.), demonstration (demonstration) etc.). (problem solving, computational and graphical work, etc.) methods were used. Explanatory method: deductive conclusion, problem statement, partial search method. Material: step-by-step development using test assignments, processing methods such as student independent work under the guidance of a teacher.

The formation of practical knowledge and skills among students of higher education institutions on the teaching of technical mechanics is carried out using a set of developed methods and teaching aids, educational goals and objectives. lum is applied in accordance with the organizational forms of training, taking into account the characteristics of the composition of a block. The learning process should be organized in such a way that students can work individually or in groups, depending on the complexity of the task. This requires different forms of teaching: individual (publications, lectures, theses, presentations, etc.), group (practical training, etc.) and group (seminars, conferences, discussions, etc.).

Conclusion. Practice shows that teaching aids affect the quality of students' knowledge, their intellectual development and professional development. Used properly, it can streamline student learning. Such tools include materials (textbooks and manuals, tables, posters, models, teaching aids, laboratory equipment, etc.) and ideal (diagrams, drawings, formulas, graphs, etc.).

Another component of the model of the process of formation of practical knowledge

among students of higher education institutions is the achievement of the planned goal, the relevance of the content and effectiveness of the process - an effective assessment component that works as a result of training: are selected organizational and management tools that include a combination of activities. The introduction of an integrated approach to the educational process contributes to the successful formation of practical knowledge among students of construction specialties in the teaching of mechanics, which involves the involvement of students in creative activities throughout the academic year. For example, the use of modern computer technology (presentations, publications, etc.), to encourage students to be active in achieving goals, to form a positive motivation for teaching and learning.

As a promising goal of the studied model, we consider the improvement of students' academic performance and its transformation into a continuous dynamic process of formation of practical knowledge and skills in the process of teaching mechanics. Thus, the gradual formation of the course "Applied Mechanics" in the field of technical mechanics, based on the structured model of the process of formation and development of practical knowledge among students in the teaching of technical mechanics in higher education institutions. In the middle there is a practical knowledge, that is, a special course is the basis for the study of technical mechanics, and practical knowledge formed in the process of studying technical mechanics is the basis for further training of students in special disciplines.

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